

1 **Replication and innate immune responses of two chikungunya virus genotypes in**
2 **human monocyte-derived macrophages**

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15

16 **ABSTRACT**

17

18 Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) is a re-emerging mosquito-borne virus which causes epidemics
19 of fever, joint pain and rash. There are three genotypes: West African,

20 East/Central/South/Africa (ECSA) and Asian, with the latter two predominant globally.

21 Genotype-specific differences in clinical presentations, virulence and immunopathology have
22 been described. Macrophages are key cells in immune responses against CHIKV. Circulating

23 blood monocytes enter tissue to differentiate into monocyte-derived macrophages (MDMs) in
24 response to CHIKV infection at key replication sites such as lymphoid organs and joints. This

25 study analyses differences in replication and induced immune mediators following infection

26 of MDMs with Asian and ECSA CHIKV genotypes. Primary human MDMs were derived
27 from residual blood donations. Replication of Asian (MY/06/37348) or ECSA (MY/08/065)

28 genotype strains of CHIKV in MDMs was measured by plaque assay. Nineteen immune

29 mediators were measured in infected cell supernatants using multiplexed immunoassay or

30 ELISA. MY/08/065 showed significantly higher viral replication at 24 hours post-infection

31 (hpi) but induced significantly lower expression of proinflammatory cytokines (CCL-2, CCL-

32 3, CCL-4, RANTES, and CXCL-10) and the anti-inflammatory IL-1Ra compared to

33 MY/06/37348. No differences were seen at later time points up to 72 hpi. During early

34 infection, MY/08/065 induced lower proinflammatory immune responses in MDMs. *In vivo*,

35 this may lead to poorer initial control of viral infection, facilitating CHIKV replication and
36 dissemination to other sites such as joints. This may explain the consistent past findings that
37 the ECSA genotype is associated with greater viremia and severity of symptoms than the
38 Asian genotype. Knowledge of CHIKV genotype-specific immunopathogenic mechanisms in
39 human MDMs is important in understanding of clinical epidemiology, biomarkers and
40 therapeutics in areas with co-circulation of different genotypes.

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43 **KEYWORDS**

44 chikungunya virus, monocyte-derived macrophages, cytokines, virus replication, immunity,
45 Malaysia

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69 INTRODUCTION

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71 Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) is a mosquito-borne alphavirus causing fever, rash and
72 arthralgia, which was first identified during an outbreak in Tanzania (Robinson, 1955). There
73 are three main genotypes, West African, East/Central/South African (ECSA), and Asian. In
74 2005, CHIKV of the ECSA genotype re-emerged and caught global attention due to an
75 epidemic in La Réunion Island, which infected 40% of the population (Borgherini *et al.*,
76 2007). Driven by increased adaptation to the *Aedes albopictus* vector and high transmission
77 rates in naïve populations, the disease spread globally in an unprecedented manner (Weaver
78 & Forrester, 2015). In 2015, CHIKV strains from the Asian genotype caused major outbreaks
79 in the Pacific Ocean islands and the Americas, previously considered to be non-endemic,
80 affecting millions (Lanciotti & Valadere, 2014). The ECSA genotype has since also become
81 established in the Americas (de Oliveira *et al.*, 2021). CHIKV has now been detected in over
82 60 countries.

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84 Monocytes and macrophages play key roles in CHIKV infection. Following a bite by an
85 infected mosquito, CHIKV replicates locally in the skin, including in macrophages, before
86 spreading to lymph nodes, spleen and liver, and subsequently via blood to secondary
87 infection sites such as muscle and joints (Sourisseau *et al.*, 2007). Infected blood monocytes
88 may play a role in dissemination (Her *et al.*, 2010). As part of the acute proinflammatory
89 response to control infection, circulating monocytes migrate into infected tissue sites and
90 differentiate into monocyte-derived macrophages (MDM) to supplement existing tissue
91 macrophages (Murray and Wynn, 2011). Innate and adaptive immunity responses then
92 control the infection, and symptoms resolve within 7-10 days. However, in some patients - up
93 to 22.5% of CHIKV patients in Malaysia (Mohd Zim *et al.*, 2013) - arthralgia may carry on
94 for months or years, particular in older adults. CHIKV persistence in macrophages within
95 chronically inflamed joints has been reported in human patients (Hoarau *et al.*, 2010) and
96 primates (Labadie *et al.*, 2010), suggesting tissue macrophages to be the main cellular
97 reservoir during chronic CHIKV inflammation.

98

99 Malaysia has experienced outbreaks of CHIKV due to two genotypes, Asian and ECSA,
100 affecting over 15,000 people between 2006 and 2010 (Sam *et al.*, 2009). The two genotypes,
101 which show about 6% nucleotide and 3% amino acid differences, demonstrated distinct
102 characteristics in virus replication in mammalian cells and mosquitoes (Sam *et al.*, 2012).

103 ECSA outbreaks have been associated with higher prevalence of disease symptoms than
104 Asian outbreaks (Bustos Carrillo *et al.*, 2019), leading to the hypothesis that clinical disease
105 may be lineage-dependent. These CHIKV genotypes may induce different immune mediator
106 profiles; in mice, infection with a Caribbean (Asian) strain was associated with a weaker pro-
107 inflammatory response within joints compared to an ECSA CHIKV strain, resulting in less
108 severe joint pathology (Gardner *et al.*, 2010; Teo *et al.*, 2015).

109

110 Comparisons of virus replication kinetics of different ECSA isolates or different CHIKV
111 genotypes have been carried out mostly in non-haematopoietic cells such as primary mouse
112 fibroblasts or muscle cancer cells (Sam *et al.*, 2012; Teo *et al.*, 2015). This study
113 hypothesized that primary human MDMs infected with Asian or ECSA genotype CHIKV
114 could have different virus replication kinetics and innate immune responses. We were
115 interested in MDMs as they are known to be phenotypically and functionally distinct from
116 tissue-resident macrophages (Murray and Wynn, 2011), which are likely important mediators
117 in chronic CHIKV arthralgia. Therefore, in this study, we analysed the differences in
118 replication and induced immune mediators following infection of MDMs with either of the
119 two CHIKV genotypes. Understanding these differences between CHIKV genotypes is
120 important when multiple genotypes are co-circulating, as there may be potential impacts on
121 disease severity and health resource allocation.

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123

124 **METHODS**

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126 **Viral stocks**

127 Malaysian CHIKV isolates used in this study were MY/06/37348 (Asian genotype, isolated
128 from a patient in Perak state in 2006, GenBank accession number FN295483) and
129 MY/08/065 (ESCA genotype, isolated from a patient from Johor state in 2008, accession
130 number FN295485). Virus isolates were serially passaged in *Mycoplasma*-free Vero cells
131 (African green monkey kidney, ATCC CCL-81), using 5% fetal bovine serum (FBS)
132 Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) as growth media. CHIKV at the fifth passage
133 (P5) was used for subsequent infection work. The infectious viruses were titrated by plaque
134 assay on Vero cells and confirmed free from *Mycoplasma* contamination.

135

136 **Human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) isolation and differentiation into**
137 **monocyte-derived macrophages (MDMs)**

138 To reduce transfusion-associated reactions, leukocytes are removed from donated blood with
139 leukocyte reduction filters, which are a useful source of leukocytes for research (Ferdowsi *et*
140 *al.*, 2021). In the Department of Transfusion Medicine in the Universiti Malaya Medical
141 Centre in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, units of 400-450 mL donated blood are leukofiltered
142 through Composelect 4F in-line leukoreduction filters (Fresenius HemoCare, Germany).
143 Filters from anonymised donors were obtained within 8 hours of use.

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145 PBMCs were extracted from elutes following back-flushing of the filters. PBMCs were
146 isolated through density gradient with Ficoll-Paque PLUS (GE Healthcare, USA) by
147 centrifugation at 400×g for 30 mins. Red blood cell lysis was performed by incubating with
148 ammonium-chloride-potassium lysing buffer for 5 minutes. Platelet depletion was carried out
149 by washing with 1× phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) 3 times at 200×g for 15 mins. To obtain
150 monocytes, T-75 Nunc cell culture flasks were seeded with 1×10⁸ PBMCs and allowed to
151 adhere for 2 hours in monocyte attachment medium (Promocell, Germany) at 37°C and 5%
152 CO₂. Non-adherent cells were removed by washing 3 times with Iscove's modified
153 Dulbecco's medium (IMDM). To differentiate the monocytes into macrophages (M0
154 macrophages), the adhered monocytes in the presence of IMDM were supplemented with
155 heat-inactivated human AB serum in a humidified incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 7 days.
156 To detach MDMs from the flask, macrophage detachment medium (Promocell) was added at
157 4°C for 4 hours followed by scraping. Cell suspensions were collected and centrifuged at
158 350×g for 15 mins. Cell pellets were resuspended in 2% heat-inactivated human AB serum
159 IMDM. MDMs were seeded into 12-well plates at 3×10⁵ cells per well. The identity of
160 MDMs were verified using anti-human CD68 antibody (BioLegend, USA), a pan-
161 macrophage marker (Supplementary Figure 1).

162

163 ***In vitro* CHIKV infection of MDMs**

164 MDMs from 8 donors were isolated and prepared independently. MDMs from each donor
165 were infected with either MY/06/37348 and MY/08/065 CHIKV isolates in parallel at
166 multiplicity of infection of 10, or 10 pfu (plaque-forming units) CHIKV/macrophage, in 2%
167 heat-inactivated human AB serum IMDM. Uninfected MDMs were included as a mock
168 control. MDMs and virus were incubated at 37°C for 4 hours. The cells were then washed 3

169 times with PBS to remove unbound virus, before fresh medium was added. This was
170 considered to be 0 hpi. The cells were then incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂. Culture
171 supernatants were harvested at 0, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hpi, and stored at -80°C.

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174 **CHIKV replication kinetics assay**

175 Virus titre in the culture supernatants was quantified using a plaque assay. Vero cells were
176 seeded at a density of 1×10^6 cells/well in 6-well cell culture plates with 2 mL of 5% FBS
177 DMEM. After overnight incubation, cells were infected with CHIKV supernatants for 1 hour
178 at 37°C. Virus inoculums were replaced with plaque media, and cells were incubated for 2
179 days. Infected cells were fixed in 3.7% paraformaldehyde and stained using crystal violet.
180 Virus titres (pfu/mL) were calculated using the formula: (number of plaques \times dilution factor)
181 / (total volume of dilution inoculated).

182

183 **Immunofluorescence assay**

184 MDMs were infected with either MY/06/37348 or MY/08/065 CHIKV isolates at MOI of 10.
185 For cell fixation, MDMs were incubated with 4% paraformaldehyde (Merck, Germany) at
186 4°C for 30 minutes. After washing twice with PBS, cells were incubated with 0.25% Triton-
187 X in PBS for 10 mins. After washing twice with PBS, cells were incubated with Image IT FX
188 signal enhancer (Sigma, USA) for 1 hour at 37°C, followed by Human TruStain FcX
189 (BioLegend) for 30 mins at room temperature (RT) and 10% heat-inactivated human AB
190 serum in PBS for 30 mins at RT. Infected MDMs were then stained using primary mouse
191 anti-alphavirus antibody (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, USA) diluted at 1:20, for 1 hour at 37
192 °C. After washing with PBS 3 times, MDMs were then incubated with a secondary antibody,
193 1:10,000 diluted goat anti-mouse Alexa Fluor 594 conjugate (BioLegend) for 1 hour at 37°C
194 in a dark chamber. MDMs were stained using 1:10,000 diluted DAPI (Thermo Fisher
195 Scientific, USA) for 10 mins at room temperature. After washing 3 times with PBS, MDMs
196 were stored at 4°C in the dark, and later visualized using a Nikon Eclipse TE2000-E inverted
197 fluorescence microscope at 20 \times objective magnification.

198

199 **Proteome profiler**

200 The Proteome Profiler Human Cytokine Array (R&D Systems, USA), which detects up to 36
201 cytokines or chemokines, was used to detect immune mediators secreted from CHIKV-

202 infected macrophages in two donors (donor 1 and donor 5) at 24 hpi and 72 hpi. Mock-
203 infected macrophages at the same timepoint were included as a baseline control. The 36
204 cytokines/chemokines were CCL-1, CCL-2, CCL-3/CCL-4, RANTES, CD40Ligand, C5,
205 CXCL-1, CXCL-10, CXCL-11, CXCL-12, G-CSF, GM-CSF, CD54, IFN- γ , IL-1 α , IL-1 β ,
206 IL-1Ra, IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-12p70, IL-13, IL-16, IL-17A, IL-17E, IL-18,
207 IL-21, IL-27, IL-32 α , MIF, PAI-1, TNF- α and TREM-1. Signal (pixel densities) on the array
208 membrane were acquired using Odyssey Infrared Imaging System and Image Studio Lite
209 software (LI-COR Biosciences, USA). The average signal for duplicate spots representing
210 each cytokine was determined. Cytokines/chemokines expressed in infected MDMs were
211 calculated as fold changes relative to mock-infected cells.

212

213 **Multiplex immunoassay**

214 The customised Magnetic Luminex Assay multiplex kit (R&D Systems) was used to further
215 measure the expression levels of 18 immune mediators (selected based on proteome profile
216 results and previous studies) in culture supernatants at 24 hpi and 72 hpi. The 18 immune
217 mediators were CCL-1, CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4, RANTES, CXCL-1, G-CSF, IFN- γ , IL-1 β ,
218 IL-1Ra, IL-8, IL-18, MIF, CXCL-9, IL-12, IFN- α , IFN- β and PTX3. The experiment was
219 carried out on samples from the 8 donors. Fluorescence readings were acquired using a
220 Luminex 200 system (Luminex Corporation, USA). The amount of each analyte bound to the
221 microparticles was quantified, capped at a maximum of 50 reads per well. Constructed
222 standard curves fell within the criteria: $R^2 > 0.995$, percentage recovery of standard between
223 70-130 %, and coefficient of variation (% CV) of replicates < 20 %. Using the standard
224 curves, expression of each immune mediator was measured in pg/mL. Analysis was
225 performed for those analytes with levels within detectable range. By default, the lowest
226 readings for each analyte were used as the lowest detection limits instead of 0 pg/mL. The
227 fold changes of immune mediators expressed in CHIKV-infected MDMs relative to mock
228 were calculated. Patterns of immune mediators are shown by one-way supervised hierarchical
229 clustering based on complete linkage analysis and Spearman's rank correlation for distance
230 measure, using online analysis tool Heatmapper (<http://www.heatmapper.ca/expression/>). The
231 significantly regulated immune mediators were uploaded to STRING Version 11.5
232 (<https://string-db.org/>) for network analysis to determine protein interaction (Szklaarczyk *et*
233 *al.*, 2021).

234

235 **CXCL-10 ELISA assay**

236 CXCL10 could not be included in the multiplex assay by the manufacturer for technical
237 reasons. Human CXCL10/IP-10 DuoSet supplemented with DuoSet ancillary reagent kit 2
238 (R&D Systems) was thus used to measure CXCL10 levels in the cell supernatants. Analysis
239 was performed for those with levels within detectable range.

240

241 **Statistical analyses**

242 Statistical analysis was conducted using GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, USA).
243 Statistical tests are stated in the figure legends. Differences were considered statistically
244 significant at $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**) and $p < 0.001$ (***).

245

246

247 **RESULTS**

248

249 **CHIKV strain MY/08/065 replicates more efficiently in MDMs**

250 MDMs were susceptible to infection of both MY/06/37348 and MY/08/065 CHIKV isolates,
251 indicated by the presence of viral antigen, although infection appeared to be at low levels
252 (Fig. 1). MDMs from 8 donors were infected with MY/06/37348 or MY/08/065 isolates at
253 MOI 10, and infectious titres were measured at 0, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hpi. No significant
254 reduction in the number of cells was observed in the MDMs over 96 hours (Supplementary
255 Figure 2). An MOI of 10 was chosen as previous papers indicated the need for higher MOIs
256 to infect monocytes/macrophages (Sourisseau *et al.*, 2007; Her *et al.*, 2010), and infection
257 with an MOI of 1 resulted in maximal virus titres of almost 1 log lower (Supplementary
258 Figure 3). Using an MOI of 10, infectious virions in the supernatants reached 10^4 pfu/mL at
259 24 hpi (Fig. 2). A significant increase in virions was detected from 0 hpi to 24 hpi ($p < 0.01$),
260 indicating active production of infectious CHIKV in MDMs. Production of virions then
261 dropped significantly from 24 hpi to 48 hpi ($p < 0.001$), 48 hpi to 72 hpi ($p < 0.001$) and 72
262 hpi to 96 hpi ($p < 0.001$). MY/08/065 produced significantly higher infectious virus at 24 hpi
263 and 48 hpi compared with MY/06/37348. This suggests that MY/08/065 replicated more
264 efficiently than MY/06/37348 in MDMs. A similar result was seen when infecting U-937
265 pro-monocytic cells differentiated into macrophages (Supplementary Figure 4) (Prasad *et al.*,
266 2020).

267

268 **Immune mediators secreted by MDMs in response to CHIKV infection**

269 To determine genotype-dependent differences in induced immune responses, a 36-plex
270 proteome profiler human cytokine array was used to detect immune mediators in the
271 supernatants of mock (uninfected), MY/06/37348-infected and MY/08/065-infected MDMs,
272 in 2 donors (donors 1 and 5) (Fig. 3). Fourteen immune mediators were identified in CHIKV-
273 infected MDMs with expression levels at >2 (upregulated) or <0.5 (downregulated) relative
274 to mock-infected MDMs, in both donors or at least 2 timepoints: CCL-1, CCL-2, CCL-3,
275 CCL-4, RANTES, CXCL-1, CXCL-10, G-CSF, IFN- γ , IL-1 β , IL-1Ra, IL-8, IL-18, and MIF.
276

277 **MY/06/37348 triggers higher chemokine/cytokine expression in macrophages at 24 hpi**

278 In addition to the 14 immune mediators of interest identified by the proteome profiler array,
279 another 5 (CXCL-9, IL-12, PTX-3, IFN- α and IFN- β) which are known to be part of the
280 immune response against CHIKV (Cook *et al.*, 2019; Guerrero-Arguero *et al.*, 2020), were
281 selected for further testing with Luminex and ELISA (CXCL-10) assays, for samples from all
282 eight donors.
283

284 Expression of 11 immune mediators was detected in infected MDMs: chemokines CCL-2,
285 CCL-3, CCL-4, RANTES, CXCL-9, and CXCL-10, cytokines IL-1Ra, IL-8, MIF, and IFN-
286 α , and the cytokine-induced protein PTX3 (summarised in Supplementary Figure 5; Figure
287 4). Levels of the remaining 8 mediators, CCL-1, CXCL-1, G-CSF, IFN- β , IFN- γ , IL-1 β , IL-
288 12 and IL-18, were below detection limits and excluded from subsequent analysis.
289

290 Patterns of immune mediators were analysed by one-way supervised hierarchical clustering
291 based on complete linkage analysis and Spearman's rank correlation for distance measure.
292 This showed that infection with MY/08/065 triggered a milder proinflammatory host
293 response compared with MY/06/37348 at 24 hpi (Supplementary Figure 5). We then
294 compared the immune mediator levels detected in mock-, MY/06/37348-, and MY/08/065-
295 infected cells. MY/06/37348 induced significantly higher CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4, RANTES,
296 IL-1Ra and CXCL-10 levels compared with MY/08/065 at 24 hpi (Fig. 4a, 4b, 4c, 4d, 4i, 4j).
297 No significant differences were seen in the cytokine profiles induced by MY/06/37348 and
298 MY/08/065 at 72 hpi (Fig. 4).
299

300 **Protein-protein interaction networks between the immune mediators**

301 The interactions among the 11 immune mediators induced in CHIKV-infected MDMs were
302 analysed using the STRING database (Fig. 5a). The protein-protein interaction (PPI) network
303 revealed 11 nodes, 30 edges, and an average node degree of 5.45. The PPI enrichment p-
304 value was $< 10^{-16}$, while the average local clustering coefficient was 0.831. Except for
305 PTX3, interactions are found among these biologically connected cytokines/chemokines.
306 CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4, CCL-5, CXCL-8, CXCL-9, and CXCL-10 are predicted to be in a
307 co-occurrence network, in which they are dependent on each other.. Physical binding
308 interaction is found between CXCL-9 and CXCL-10, and they are part of a physical complex.
309 The PPI enriched notably for C-C chemokine receptor 1 (CCR1) chemokine receptor binding
310 under molecular function (3 proteins; Fig. 5b), positive regulation of natural killer cell
311 chemotaxis under biological process (3 proteins; Fig. 5c), and viral protein interaction with
312 cytokine and chemokine receptor under the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
313 (KEGG) (7 proteins; Fig. 5d).

314

315

316 **DISCUSSION**

317 Asian and ECSA are the major CHIKV genotypes causing global outbreaks since 2005. We
318 showed that MDMs were susceptible to CHIKV strains of both genotypes, with MY/08/065
319 (ECSA) replicating to higher levels than MY/06/37348 (Asian), and MY/08/065 eliciting
320 lower proinflammatory mediators (CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4, RANTES, and CXCL-10) and the
321 anti-inflammatory IL-1Ra at 24 hpi. Infectious titres in MDMs increased til 24 hpi with a
322 decline thereafter and were low (10^2 to 10^4 pfu/ml) overall, as previously reported (Felipe *et*
323 *al.*, 2020; Sourisseau *et al.*, 2007). The lower viral production by macrophages cannot
324 explain the high viremia (10^4 to 10^8 pfu/ml) detected in plasma of acutely infected patients
325 (Chow *et al.*, 2011). The main contribution to viremia is likely from non-hematopoietic
326 (epithelial, endothelial, fibroblasts and musculoskeletal) cells known to produce higher
327 CHIKV titres, while hematopoietic cells such as lymphocytes, dendritic cells, and NK cells
328 are refractory to CHIKV (Sourisseau *et al.*, 2007; van Duijl-Richter *et al.*, 2015).

329

330 We found that CHIKV-infected MDMs produced increased inflammatory factors, including
331 CXCL-9, CXCL-10, MIF, CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4, RANTES, and IL-1Ra. Downregulation
332 of IL-8, seen in this study, is a possible biomarker for severe CHIKV disease (Her *et al.*,
333 2010). The major proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and IL-6, reported as biomarkers in

334 acutely infected patients, were poorly expressed in infected MDMs in this study, as
335 previously noted (Ng *et al.*, 2009). IL-6 in blood may originate from other cells such as
336 osteoblasts (Noret *et al.*, 2012), skeletal muscle (Lentscher *et al.*, 2020), or tissue
337 macrophages, as high levels of IL-6 are present in synovial fluid of patients with chronic
338 arthralgia (Hoarau *et al.*, 2010). Low levels of IL-1 β are consistent with the high levels of IL-
339 1Ra, which antagonizes IL-1 α and IL-1 β (McIntyre *et al.*, 1991). The chemotaxis
340 chemokines CCL-3, CCL-4, and RANTES may also inhibit IL-1 β release from monocytic
341 cells (Amati *et al.*, 2017). Expression of CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4, and RANTES are associated
342 with improved clinical phenotype in CHIKV-infected mice (Fox *et al.*, 2019), suggesting
343 their role as viral suppressor factors. High expression of proinflammatory chemotactic CCL-
344 2, which directs the infiltration of active monocytes/macrophages, was detected in synovial
345 fluid of CHIKV-infected patients (Hoarau *et al.*, 2010).

346
347 IFNs were previously reported at high levels in patient monocytes and serum (Her *et al.*,
348 2010; Teng *et al.*, 2015). However, we found low or undetectable levels of IFN- α , IFN- β and
349 IFN- γ . Others showed that CHIKV induces IFN production not from macrophages (Kumar *et*
350 *al.*, 2012; Valdés-López *et al.*, 2021), but from fibroblasts (Schilte *et al.*, 2010).

351 Antiviral responses against CHIKV and DENV were also reported to be largely independent
352 of the type I interferon pathway (Olagnier *et al.*, 2014). Both CXCL-9 and CXCL-10, which
353 share the same CXC receptor 3 and were highly expressed in this study, are associated with
354 higher symptom severity during acute infection (Kelvin *et al.*, 2011). Deficiency in the
355 stimulator-of-interferon-genes pathway has been associated with aberrant elevation in CXCL-
356 10 expression, which can contribute to pathogenesis of arthritogenic alphaviruses (Geng *et*
357 *al.*, 2020). Overexpressed MIF is associated with alphavirus-induced arthritis by CHIKV and
358 Ross River virus (Herrero *et al.*, 2011). Knowledge that certain cytokines are elevated during
359 CHIKV infection may provide possible therapeutic targets. For example, this study showed
360 increased CXCL-10 and CCL-2; inhibitors atorvastatin (Lin *et al.*, 2020) and bindarit (Chen
361 *et al.*, 2015) have been tested against CHIKV in mice.

362

363 CHIKV infection in MDMs induced cytokines involved in CCR1 chemokine receptor
364 binding and positive regulation of NK cell chemotaxis (Fig. 5). CCR1 involvement was
365 associated with severe acute disease in mice (Jain *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, CCL-3 and
366 RANTES, which are ligands for CCR1 receptor, are possible biomarkers for severe CHIKV

367 (Ng *et al.*, 2009). MDMs potentially express chemokines CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4 and
368 RANTES to recruit NK cells for viral clearance. NK cells play a vital role in acute infection
369 via cytotoxic activity by releasing IFN- γ and granzyme B (Teo *et al.*, 2015). In addition,
370 NKG2C receptors expressed on NK cells are involved in CHIKV sensing and clearance
371 (Petitdemange *et al.*, 2011). However, NK cells may also contribute to acute and chronic
372 CHIKV-induced arthralgia, as their depletion reduced joint swelling in mice (Teo *et al.*,
373 2013), and patients with chronic joint disease have synovial infiltrates of macrophages
374 containing detectable CHIKV antigens, NK and T cells (Hoarau *et al.*, 2010).

375

376 Several studies have shown CHIKV genotype differences in immune responses and
377 virulence, with ECSA apparently more virulent than Asian genotype. ECSA outbreaks were
378 associated with less frequent asymptomatic disease compared to Asian outbreaks in
379 Nicaragua and the Philippines (Bustos Carrillo *et al.*, 2019). High viraemia levels were
380 associated with increased disease severity in DBA/1J and A129 mice, and cynomolgus and
381 rhesus macaques, with West African CHIKV strains the most pathogenic, followed by ECSA,
382 then Asian strains (Julander *et al.*, 2020; Langsjoen *et al.*, 2018; Chen *et al.*, 2010). In mice,
383 ECSA-IOL CHIKV induced higher levels of immune cell infiltrates and pro-inflammatory
384 mediators in joints, and foot swelling than the Asian genotype (Gardner *et al.*, 2010; Teo *et*
385 *al.*, 2015). However, these studies analysed blood or joint tissue/fluid, representing the
386 overall immune response, without targeting specific cell types like MDMs.

387

388 Monocytes/macrophages play several roles during CHIKV infection. CHIKV replicates at
389 low levels in monocytes, which may help bloodstream dissemination (Her *et al.*, 2010). The
390 virus disseminates to lymphoid organs such as spleen, lymph nodes and liver, and joints and
391 muscle, and this is followed by macrophage infiltration (Labadie *et al.*, 2010). These
392 macrophages originate from circulating monocytes which migrate from blood to tissue and
393 differentiate into MDMs to supplement tissue-resident macrophages, particularly during
394 infection or cell damage (Murray and Wynn, 2011). Tissue macrophages (such as synovial
395 macrophages implicated in CHIKV-induced arthritis) are generally of embryonic origin and
396 found in all vertebrate tissues from mid-gestation (Hannemann *et al.*, 2021). Macrophages
397 display wide heterogeneity in phenotype and function, depending on origin and location, and
398 signals received from the microenvironment. Macrophages exist on a continuum between a
399 pro-inflammatory M1 phenotype and an anti-inflammatory/tissue repair M2 phenotype.

400 Following an initial pro-inflammatory response to control an infection, there is a switch to an
401 anti-inflammatory process to promote wound healing; dysregulation of this balance leads to
402 severe acute disease or chronic inflammation (Ordaz-Arias *et al.*, 2022). Macrophage
403 phenotype impacts permissiveness to infection, viral replication and immune signaling (Fear
404 *et al.*, 1998; Lee & Ghiasi, 2017), and this includes clear differences between MDMs and
405 tissue macrophages (Gundra *et al.*, 2014).

406

407 The different immune responses elicited by CHIKV following infection of different cells of
408 the monocyte/macrophage lineage are not clearly understood. One study showed that CHIKV
409 infection induced higher pro-inflammatory cytokines in monocytes than MDMs (Felipe *et al.*,
410 2020). In CHIKV-infected mice, clodronate treatment to deplete macrophages both
411 prolonged viremia and decreased joint swelling, suggesting that macrophages are important
412 for virus clearance and joint inflammation (Gardner *et al.*, 2010). Thus,
413 monocytes/macrophages are implicated in a range of sometimes contradictory roles,
414 including target of infection, vehicle of dissemination, viral clearance, and severity of joint
415 inflammation. The diverse monocytes, MDMs and tissue macrophages within this cell
416 lineage are involved to varying degrees in these roles.

417

418 The present study shows that MDMs have a less robust pro-inflammatory response and
419 poorer control of infection by ECSA CHIKV compared to Asian CHIKV. As MDMs play an
420 early role in controlling CHIKV in important replication sites such as lymphoid organs, this
421 may contribute to the higher viraemia reported in several studies of ECSA CHIKV, which in
422 turn may lead to greater viral dissemination to key organs such as joints. This may explain
423 the more severe pathology observed in joints (mediated by tissue macrophages) after ECSA
424 CHIKV infection compared to Asian CHIKV (Gardner *et al.*, 2010).

425

426 There were some limitations in this study. *In vitro* generated MDMs do not replicate the
427 natural physiological state, and do not represent all macrophage phenotypes which vary
428 widely by tissue locations and origins. It would be interesting to study the differences in
429 immune responses between monocytes, MDMs and tissue macrophages during different
430 stages of CHIKV infection. Only one CHIKV isolate was used to represent each of the two
431 genotypes, and more clinical strains should be studied. More immune analytes should be
432 included in future work, such as IL-7, IL-15, IL-27, TGF- β , eotaxin, HGF, and Mxra8
433 receptor, which have all been associated with CHIKV severity (Ferreira *et al.*, 2021).

434

435 In conclusion, we showed that during early viral infection of MDMs, CHIKV of the ECSA
436 genotype triggered lower proinflammatory mediators and replicated to higher levels than an
437 Asian genotype virus. Further work is needed to understand the specific roles of MDMs
438 within the monocyte/macrophage lineage and how this results in the more severe symptoms
439 and joint pathology described following infection with ECSA viruses compared to Asian
440 viruses. Both genotypes circulate globally, and are present in some countries like Malaysia.
441 Understanding differences in immune responses to both genotypes is important to explain
442 differences in clinical severity and responses to drugs and vaccines. Immune mediator
443 signatures may also be used as biomarkers to distinguish between CHIKV infection of
444 different genotypes and for disease severity, and the mediators themselves may be potential
445 therapeutic targets.

446

447

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459 Conceptualization: C.L.C., I-C.S. Funding acquisition: C.L.C., Y.F.C., I-C.S. Methodology:
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464 C.L.C., Y.F.C., I-C.S.

465

466 **Conflicts of interest**

467 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

468

469 **Ethical statement**

470 This study was approved by the Universiti Malaya Medical Centre Medical Research Ethics
471 Committee (reference no. 2017714-5408).

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706 **Figure labels**

707

708 **Fig. 1. MDMs were susceptible to MY/06/37348 and MY/08/065 CHIKV isolates.** MDMs

709 were infected with MY/06/37348 or MY/08/065 isolates at MOI 10. Cell nuclei were stained
710 with DAPI (blue) and the presence of CHIKV antigen was detected by Alexa Fluor 594 (red).

711 Scale bar, 20 μ m. Objective magnification: 20 \times .

712

713 **Fig. 2. Virus replication of MY/08/065 and MY/06/37348 in infected MDMs.** (a) MDMs

714 from 8 donors were infected with either virus isolate MY/06/37348 (Asian; red circles) or

715 MY/08/065 (ECSA; blue squares) at MOI of 10; (b) replication of CHIKV in MDMs of the

716 eight donors combined, showing median (\pm 95% CI) virus titres. Comparison between virus

717 strains was performed with the two-tailed Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test, at $p <$

718 0.05 (*), $p <$ 0.01 (**), and $p <$ 0.001 (***). The dotted line marks the lowest detection limit

719 for virus titers. A titer of 1 indicates no detectable growth.

720

721 **Fig. 3. Immune mediators expressed in CHIKV-infected MDMs measured by proteome**

722 **profiler human cytokine array.** Immune mediator levels are shown as fold changes relative

723 to mock in the supernatants of (a) donor 1, at 24 hpi and (b) 72 hpi; (c) donor 5, at 24 hpi and

724 (d) 72 hpi. The thresholds at \log_2 (fold changes) of 1 and -1 are shown as dashed lines. Fold-

725 changes >2 or <0.5 were considered to be biologically significant.

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727

728 **Fig. 4. MY/06/37348 induces significantly higher expressions of CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-4,**

729 **RANTES, IL-1Ra and CXCL-10 compared with MY/08/065 in MDMs.** Dot plots of

730 expression levels of immune mediators in MY/06/37348-infected and MY/08/065-infected

731 MDMs from 8 donors at 24 and 72 hpi. Comparisons between mock-, MY/06/37348- and

732 MY/08/065-infected MDMs were made using the Friedman test followed by post-hoc testing

733 using the 2-stage step-up method of Benjamini, Krieger and Yekutieli with a false discovery

734 rate [q] set at 0.05. Immune mediators shown here are: (a) CCL-2, (b) CCL-4, (c) CCL-3, (d)

735 RANTES, (e) IFN- α , (f) IL-8, (g) CXCL-9, (h) MIF, (i) IL-1Ra, (j) CXCL-10, and (k) PTX3.

736 The dashed lines mark the lowest detection limits for each analyte. Significance levels are p
737 < 0.05 (*) and p < 0.001 (**), and refer to the post-hoc comparisons between MY/06/37348-
738 and MY/08/065-infected MDMs.

739

740 **Fig. 5. Protein-protein interaction network showing confidence of the associations**
741 **between the 11 immune mediators detected in CHIKV-infected MDMs.** (a) The
742 functional and physical protein interaction map was generated using default settings. Only
743 interactions with confidence scores ≥ 0.7 are shown, indicating medium confidence that a
744 predicted link exists between two enzymes in the KEGG database. The thickness of each line
745 indicates the degree of confidence of an association. Coloured nodes indicate proteins
746 associated with CCR1 chemokine receptor binding (blue), positive regulation of natural killer
747 cell chemotaxis (red), and interaction with cytokine and chemokine receptors (green). (b)
748 Enrichment analysis by biological process. (c) Enrichment analysis by molecular function.
749 (d) Enrichment analysis by KEGG.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 4a-f

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Figure 5

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Figure 3

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Supplementary materials:

Supplementary Figure 1. Confirmation of monocyte-derived macrophages (MDMs) by immunofluorescent staining. (a) Macrophages under the microscope; (b) DAPI was used as counterstaining for nuclei (blue); (c) MDMs were stained with a pan-macrophage marker anti-human CD68 Y1/82A (red). Scale bar, 20 μ m. Objective magnification: 20 \times .

Supplementary Figure 2. Daily observation of CHIKV-infected MDMs at 0, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hpi. Mock-infected MDMs (a-e) and MDMs infected with either virus isolate MY/06/37348 (f-j) or MY/08/065 (k-o) are shown. Scale bar, 20 μ m. Objective magnification: 20 \times .

Supplementary Figure 3. Virus titration of MY/08/065 and MY/06/37348 in infected MDMs. MDMs from donor 9 were infected with either virus isolate MY/06/37348 (Asian; red circles) or MY/08/065 (ECSA; blue squares) at an MOI of 1. Median (\pm 95% CI) virus titres are shown. The dotted line marks the lowest detection limit for virus titres.

Supplementary Figure 4. Virus titration of MY/08/065 and MY/06/37348 in infected U-937 cells. U-937 is a pro-monocytic cell line (ATCC CRL-1593.2) which was grown in 10% FBS Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium and differentiated into macrophages by incubation with 5 μ g/ml phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 4 days (Prasad *et al.*, 2020). Cells were infected with either virus isolate MY/06/37348 (Asian; red circles) or MY/08/065 (ECSA; blue squares) at an MOI of 10. Two independent biological replicates were performed, and median (\pm 95% CI) virus titres are shown. The dotted line marks the lowest detection limit for virus titres. A titre of 1 indicates no detectable growth.

Supplementary Figure 5. MY/06/37348 induces higher chemokine and proinflammatory cytokine expression than MY/08/065 in MDMs. Cytokine and chemokine levels in the supernatants of mock-, MY/06/37348- and MY/08/065-infected MDMs (n = 8 donors per group) were quantified using ELISA (CXCL-10 only) and Luminex assays at 24 hpi or 72 hpi. Patterns of immune mediators are shown by one-way supervised hierarchical clustering based on complete linkage analysis and Spearman's rank correlation for distance measure. Each row represents one of the 11 cytokines and each column represents one sample. The expression level of each analyte was normalised across all MDMs. Samples from mock (n=8), MY/06/37348-infected (n=8), or MY/08/065-infected (n=8) groups are arranged from left to right. Colours represent scaled expression values of the z-score in each row/analyte, ranging from red for low expression to green for high expression levels. PTX3 was detected only at 72 hpi.